

UUID – Versions & Timestamps

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Detlef Burkhardt

[FOSSEA³M](#)

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ORCID: [0009-0000-9155-716X](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9155-716X)

Introduction

A UUID (Universally Unique Identifier) is a 128-bit identifier that can be generated globally without a central authority. Standardization is managed by the IETF (Internet Engineering Task Force). The current standard RFC 9562 (May 2024) supersedes the long-standing predecessor RFC 4122 (2005) and introduces the new versions v6, v7, and v8.

Structure of a UUID

A UUID consists of 32 hexadecimal characters arranged in five groups in the format 8-4-4-4-12:

```
xxxxxxxx - xxxx - Mxxx - Nxxx - xxxxxxxxxxxxxx
```

The character **M** (13th position) encodes the **version**, the character **N** (17th position) encodes the **variant** (always 8, 9, a, or b under RFC 4122 and RFC 9562). The remaining bits carry a timestamp, random data, or application-defined content depending on the version.

Example: 66dc3dbc - 4418 - **8**000 - b971 - 4d1a366d72b0 → Version **8**

UUID Versions at a Glance

Versions are standardized by the IETF. RFC 9562 (2024) is the current successor to RFC 4122 (2005).

Version	Release	Standard	Timestamp	Method
v1	1997	RFC 4122	yes	60-bit, 100 ns steps since 15 Oct 1582 + MAC address
v2	1997	DCE 1.1	yes	Like v1 + POSIX UID. Rarely used.
v3	2005	RFC 4122	no	MD5 hash of namespace + name. Deterministic.
v4	2005	RFC 4122	no	122 random bits. No date recoverable.
v5	2005	RFC 4122	no	SHA-1 hash of namespace + name. Deterministic.
v6	2024	RFC 9562	yes	Redesign of v1, timestamp sortable for databases.
v7	2024	RFC 9562	yes	Unix timestamp in milliseconds in the first 48 bits.
v8	2024	RFC 9562	application-defined	Only version/variant bits standardized, rest is free.

RFC 9562 also defines two special cases: the **Nil UUID** (all bits zero, representing a null value) and the **Max UUID** (all bits set, representing the maximum value). Both are useful as sentinel values in application protocols.

Choosing the Right Version

For most use cases the following rule of thumb applies:

v4 is the default choice when no time reference is needed and maximum simplicity is desired. **v7** is recommended for database primary keys, since the Unix timestamp in the first 48 bits provides natural sort order by creation time. **v5** is the right choice when the same inputs (namespace + name) must always reproducibly yield the same UUID, for example for canonical resource identifiers. **v8** offers a free canvas for custom schemas within the UUID framework, as long as the version and variant bits are set correctly.

Identifying the Version

The 13th character of the UUID (first character of the third block) always encodes the version:

66dc3dbc-4418-**8**000-b971-4d1a366d72b0 → Version **8**

90be90a3-fedc-**4**18b-b122-9037203b8015 → Version **4**

OpenAI's UUIDv8 Implementation

OpenAI encodes a Unix timestamp in seconds in the first 32 bits (8 hex characters). The switch from UUIDv4 to UUIDv8 demonstrably took place around 7 September 2024.

Extracting the timestamp requires only a few lines of code: the first 8 hex characters are read as an integer and interpreted as Unix epoch seconds. The Python snippet below illustrates the principle – readers not working with Python may skip this section; the logic is fully described in the previous sentence.

```
from datetime import datetime, timezone

def uuid_to_created_at(uuid):
    version = int(uuid.replace('-', '')[12], 16)
    if version == 8:
        ts = int(uuid.replace('-', '')[:8], 16)
        return datetime.fromtimestamp(ts, tz=timezone.utc).strftime('%Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%SZ')
    return None # UUIDv4 → no date available
```

UUID Prefixes as a Heuristic

The first 2 hex characters reflect the timestamp range in UUIDv8 and can serve as a quick recognition aid. For reliable identification, however, the 13th character should always be checked, since prefixes such as 66 and 67 can appear in both versions.

Open Questions

1. The first 32 bits encode seconds. UUIDv7 would offer milliseconds. Is this a deliberate decision by OpenAI?
2. Can the timestamp range be used to infer the server time or timezone?
3. What further metadata could be derived from UUIDv8 implementations?

References

- IETF RFC 9562 (2024): *Universally Unique Identifiers (UUIDs)*.
<https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc9562>
- IETF RFC 4122 (2005): *A Universally Unique Identifier (UUID) URN Namespace*.
<https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc4122>
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